

HIGHER EDUCATION AS A COMPETITIVE ENTERPRISE - AN OVERVIEW

***Miss.Manu K B,**

Faculty Member, MBA Department,

Sahyadri College Campus,

Kuvempu University, Shivamogga.

****Mrs.Ramya H S,**

Research Scholar, Shivamogga.

Abstract:

An academic revolution has taken place in higher education in the past half century marked by transformations unprecedented in scope and diversity. Comprehending this ongoing and dynamic process while being in the midst of it is not an easy task. The academic changes of the late 20th and early 21st centuries are more extensive due to their global nature and the number of institutions and people they affect. In the early 21st century, higher education has become a competitive enterprise. In many countries students must compete for scarce places in universities and in all countries admission to the top institutions has become more difficult. Universities compete for status and ranking, and generally for funding from governmental or private sources. While competition has always been a force in academe and can help produce excellence, it can also contribute to a decline in a sense of academic community, mission and traditional values. The global economy is promoted as being a 'knowledge economy', which is used to justify ongoing attempts to increase participation rates in higher education. But if governments continue to move away from the 'higher education as public good' approach, higher education will continue to become more marketised and less research focused.

Higher education has been placed at the centre of public debate as a result of the 2008 financial collapse and the ongoing economic crisis. The main thrust of the issue centres around a rejustification of the role of higher education and a redefinition of its funding relationship with government. It is important because the economic crisis has changed higher education at both the micro and macro levels. The immediate shorter-term impact of the economic crisis has been at the institutional micro level where as it is more important in the longer-term impact of the economic crisis on macro planning and policy of higher education. The economic crisis has legitimized the long-existing argument that higher education should be treated the same as any other service in the economy and, as such, should be subject to ever-more accountability and managerialist practices.

Key words: Transformation, Economic Crisis, Rejustification, Redefinition, Accountability.

Introduction:

Our educational system is inadequate to provide quality education to all the aspiring millions. The National Knowledge Commission (2009) estimates that our country needs to build 1500 universities in the next 10 years to cope with the demand of higher education and to sustain growth. This requires huge investment by the government where we are lacking. Increasingly Indian governments attempting to turn direct funding and public debt into indirect funding via student loan and private debt. This transformation serves the macroeconomic objectives of governments and legitimizes talk about students getting ‘value for money’ and a ‘return on their investment’ in a ‘services provider- customer’ model of higher education. The higher education institutions now have to pursue plans to create alternative streams of income more aggressively, while imposing severe cuts on their provision by cutting academic programmes that are not competitive. As a result, higher education policy has entered a phase of extreme rationalisation with an emphasis on ‘cutting the excess fat’ and ‘balancing the budget’. It seems that the economic crisis has created a neo-liberal policy and management framework in

higher education that has resulted in moves to shift the financial burden for higher education from governments to students and their families.

The growth of transnational higher education providers in the source countries of international students, coupled with a wider acceptance of transnational provision as a recognized form of higher education, has made it more attractive. Hence the capacity of the global economy has increased to create enough jobs for graduates.

Literature Review:

1. **Samoff (1994)** noted that observers have reported structural adjustment policies often encourage an emphasis on inappropriate skills and reproduce existing social and economic inequalities, leading actually to lowered enrollment rates, degradation in the quality of education, and a gap between educational needs and provisions.
2. **Vangelis Tsigiris**, in his article noted that the higher education will be shaped by pursuit monetary objectives and lack of regulation leads the problem of consumer protection and creates significant risks in the unregulated transnational higher educational activities.
3. **UNESCO Bangkok**, in its study reveals the aim of this research is to build Knowledge about trends and discontinuities, commonalities and diversity, challenges and opportunities, successes and failures in various system of education.
4. **Molly Carbett Board**, President, American Council on education, in the study specifies the recession has brought about a series of transformative trends that will endure long past the current Economic movement and fundamentally change our higher education system.
5. **Navin Singh**, Rosemary Papa, in their study mentioned that the forces associated with the global crisis have the content in which educators operate and profoundly changed ones experience in both formal and informal education.

Objectives:

1. To study the effect of global crisis on higher education in India.

2. To analyze the factors influencing higher education.
3. To study the role of government in bringing effectiveness in higher education.

Overview of the study:

Higher education has undergone tremendous expansion in the recent past. The growing employment opportunities and the increased skills needed to compete in the global labor market are important reasons for the expansion of the sector. This paper argues that higher education in the context of globalization has become a market-determined process, replacing the near monopoly enjoyed by the state. The growth of private and cross-border higher education reflects this change. The paper discusses cross-border education through three different forms – through the mobility of institutions, of students, and of teachers. Cross-border student mobility is encouraged since it is a good source of getting future highly skilled workers in certain specialized areas. Institutional mobility is very often from the developed to less developed countries. Student mobility, on the other hand, is from the less developed to developed countries.

1. NavinSingh, Rosemary Papa, “Impact of Globalization in Higher Education”, volume-5, number 2(April-June,2012)

The United States of America (USA) is the preferred destination for cross-border education and nearly three fourths of all cross-border students are hosted by 10 member countries of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The current economic crisis, although it started from the financial systems of the developed countries, is global in its reach as it spreads to both middle- and low-income countries. The initial indications are that the crisis will result in heavy losses in employment and in household income levels. The crisis may lead to reduced funding for education from all sources – government, private sector and households. Many universities with investments in foreign banks have already lost their investments. Student support systems, scholarships and student loans will be severely affected.

Some of the largest providers of student loans have lost heavily during the crisis, and some of them have failed for bankruptcy protection in 2008. The financial crisis may lead to a freeze on recruitment and a cut in programmes. The crisis may also lead to reduced aid flows. This paper points out that leaving the education sector to markets may not be a good option. It argues for active state intervention in higher education. There is a need to redefine the role of the state in the changed circumstances. The ideal situation would have been full state funding but it has to be recognized that the state has an important role to play, even when it does not have adequate resources to finance the higher education sector. The state needs to take responsibility for developing rules for establishing private and cross-border institutions, for putting in place mechanisms to ensure quality and regulations to ensure equity. Given the limited resources at its disposal, the state may better target its limited resources to disadvantaged groups to improve overall equity in higher education.

2. Molly Carbett Board, President, American Council on education, “Higher Education in 2012: a global perspective”

3. Vangelis Tsigiris, “the impact of economic crisis on Higher Education”, 18th March 2012, Issue No 213.

4. UNESCO Bangkok, “Asia and Pacific regional Beareau for Education”, ISBN 978-9223-400-3.

Factors affecting effectiveness of higher education:

The literature clearly indicates that there are various factors which directly or indirectly influence the effectiveness (Quality) in technical education. Here we group these factors under seven broad heads as discussed below

[A] Administration

[B] Infrastructure

[C] Teaching Effectiveness

[D] Students

[E] Interaction with Industry and Society

[F] Extra Curricular Activities

[G] Research and Development

A. Administration [A]

The administration of technical institution play vital role in its functioning and its responsibilities includes-

1. Setting objectives for the functioning of the institution.
2. Formulating policies and programs to achieve it.
3. Controlling all the functions which directly or indirectly affect the efficiency.

B. Infrastructure [B]

“We shape our institution and our institution shapes us”, Winston Churchill. An institution must have adequate land, necessary buildings, hostels, supporting facilities, canteen, transport, library, well equipped laboratories and workshop availabilities of teaching aids like OHP, LCD projector, seminar halls conference room and last but not lest advance computing facilities. These facilities are initial prerequisite for any technical institution which must be present to ensure proper functioning of Technical Institution.

C. Teaching Effectiveness[C]

The quality of students coming out of the universities and colleges largely depends upon the quality of the teaching staff employed. The frontier of science and technology are doubling by leaps and bounds to cope with it its necessary, for the faculty to be constantly in touch with the same and try to update themselves through enhancing their qualifications attend various quality improvement programs like workshops, seminars, conference, summer and winter school etc. is

the responsibility of the institution to provide a proper and conducive atmosphere for the teacher.

D. Students [D]

The students constitute the input of the whole system. The accomplishment of the process of imparting knowledge is greatly affected by environment in which the students are put and also on their self zeal to learn and excel. A student's own awareness and interest for learning and the inherent aptitude to grasp together with his sincerity, regularity and honesty are key to his successful accomplishment of his course. It is also necessary to boost the moral of the students by motivating the students. All these aspects when carefully implemented and nurtured bring about a total turn around in the quality of education.

E. Interaction with Industry and Society [E]

The fresh engineers from technical institution need to be offered training in industries to give them first hand practical exposure. There is a need for general recasting of curricula, with industry oriented programs and to establish a close link between an educational program and social needs.

F. Extra Curricular Activities [F]

Good education in its totality must include the overall development of the student and must not restrict to training in a specialized discipline. The institution must organize various extra-curricular activities like arranging group discussions, debates, technical quizzes, extempore, guest lectures, seminars and promote NCC, NSS, sports, games, cultural and co- curricular activities. These extra curricular activities enhance and improve the inherent capabilities and skill of the students.

G. Research and Development [G]

Research and development activity is very much essential to survive in this competitive world. The institution must have proper infrastructure to carry out research and development activities

. The students must have access to scientific Journals and other modern library facilities. There must be availability of qualified and experienced research oriented and motivated faculty. Adequate financial provision must be present to carry out research activities.

Role of Government in Higher Education:

Higher education system in India is fairly large and complex. Within the system, the Central government is primarily involved in policy decisions and state governments are engaged in funding activities. The central government's role involves establishment, grants and oversight of institutes of higher education and it discharges its activities through UGC and other professional councils. State governments, which play a major role in funding of institutes through operating as well as capital grants, carry out most functions through the concerned government department or directorate of the respective states. The role of the Central government in funding institutes of higher education is quiet limited and uneven. With a handful of central institutions catering to around 2 per cent of the students getting nearly 85 per cent of central allocation for higher education, state governments end up being responsible for providing bulk of public funding. According to the report of the CABE Committee on financing of higher and technical education, state governments account for more than three-fourths of the total government expenditure on higher education. However, in case of technical education, the Union and state governments share the financial responsibility almost equally. In the late eighties, state governments grappled with issues related to unprecedented demand for quality higher education for a growing population. Over the years, different states tried various methods for fulfilling this requirement; for instance, they allowed entry of private players and tried out different models of financing based on fees and merit. Some states also drew flak from some quarters in the public who felt the administration was diluting the quality of education by bringing in the commercial aspect in an otherwise social sector. In response to these adverse public reactions, Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, and Maharashtra enacted laws regulating admission and prohibiting capitation fee in private unaided professional institutions in 1983, 1984, and 1987, respectively, and thus, opened doors for judicial intervention. Presently, state governments are struggling with

the ever-increasing financial burden on the one hand and the need to maintain quality of education on the other. Central Government is responsible for major policy relating to higher education in the country. It provides grants to the UGC and establishes central universities in the country. The Central Government is also responsible for declaration of Educational Institutions as 'Deemed to be University' on the recommendation of the UGC. Presently there are sixteen (18) Central Universities in the country. In pursuance of the Mizoram Accord, another Central University in the State of Mizoram is planned. There are 99 Institutions which have been declared as Deemed to be Universities by the Govt. of India as per Section of the UGC Act, 1956. State Governments are responsible for establishment of State Universities and colleges, and provide plan grants for their development and non-plan grants for their maintenance. The coordination and cooperation between the Union and the States is brought about in the field of education through the Central Advisory Board of Education (CABE). Special Constitutional responsibility of the Central Government: Education is on the 'Concurrent list' subject to Entry 66 in the Union List of the Constitution. This gives exclusive Legislative Power to the Central Govt. for co-ordination and determination of standards in Institutions of higher education or research and scientific and technical institutions.

The National Literacy Mission aims at achieving 85 per cent literacy at the end of the Eleventh 5-year plan (2007-2012). In order to achieve higher literacy rates, the government has been initiating programmes such as the Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan, which aims at achieving universal elementary education of satisfactory quality by 2010. Furthermore, the development of an Educational Development Index (EDI) for elementary education is perceived as a significant step towards imparting quality education. The country's present education system comprises elementary, secondary and higher education, which consists of undergraduate, post graduate and professional degree and diploma courses. Following Table shows the growth of Indian education institutions during 1950-2006.

Growth in student's enrolment:

Higher education in India has scaled up gradually from 20 universities and 500 colleges at the time of independence to 416 universities and 20,677 colleges currently. These comprise of 251 state universities, 24 central universities, 103 deemed universities, 5 institutions established under state legislations and 33 institutes of national importance established by central legislation. At the start of the academic year 2007-08, the total number of students enrolled for higher education stood at 11.6 million; of which 12.94 per cent were enrolled in university departments and 87.06 per cent in affiliated colleges. More than 80 per cent of the students are enrolled in three faculties of arts, science and commerce/management whereas the rest are enrolled in professional courses with the highest percentage in engineering and technology followed by medical sciences. It is interesting to note that in India, where agriculture and allied constituents play a critical role in economic development, student enrolment in agricultural courses accounts for around only 0.5 per cent. Enrolment of female students grew phenomenally from less than 10 per cent of total enrolment during independence to around 40 per cent in 2005-06. Likewise, the number of women colleges also increased in the last decade from 1,146 to 1,902 in 2005-06. The faculty of arts accounted for more than 50 per cent of the total female student enrolments. Kerala, Goa and Punjab were the three top states in terms of female student enrolment and their respective female student enrolments in the total enrolments were 61 per cent, 59.2 per cent, and 51.7 per cent and during 2010-11 we can see the increase rate in all the mentioned educational factors.

Growth of Higher Education Institutions:

<i>years</i>	<i>Primary</i>	<i>Upper primary</i>	<i>Sec/ Pre .Jr colleges</i>	<i>Colleges for general education</i>	<i>profes sional education</i>	<i>Deemed univ</i>
<i>1950-51</i>	<i>209.70</i>	<i>13.60</i>	<i>7.40</i>	<i>0.40</i>	<i>0.20</i>	<i>0.03</i>
<i>1960-61</i>	<i>330.40</i>	<i>49.70</i>	<i>17.30</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.90</i>	<i>0.05</i>
<i>1965-66</i>	<i>408.40</i>	<i>90.60</i>	<i>37.10</i>	<i>2.30</i>	<i>1.00</i>	<i>0.08</i>
<i>1970-71</i>	<i>494.50</i>	<i>118.60</i>	<i>51.60</i>	<i>3.40</i>	<i>3.50</i>	<i>0.11</i>
<i>1975-76</i>	<i>560.90</i>	<i>151.50</i>	<i>79.80</i>	<i>4.90</i>	<i>0.90</i>	<i>0.18</i>
<i>1980-81</i>	<i>638.70</i>	<i>206.30</i>	<i>126.00</i>	<i>7.90</i>	<i>2.20</i>	<i>0.25</i>
<i>1985-86</i>	<i>664.00</i>	<i>219.60</i>	<i>133.50</i>	<i>8070</i>	<i>2.24</i>	<i>0.27</i>
<i>1990-91</i>	<i>651.40</i>	<i>245.30</i>	<i>137.20</i>	<i>9.20</i>	<i>2.60</i>	<i>0.30</i>
<i>1995-96</i>	<i>712.20</i>	<i>262.30</i>	<i>146.00</i>	<i>9.40</i>	<i>2.80</i>	<i>0.41</i>
<i>2000-01</i>	<i>767.50</i>	<i>274.70</i>	<i>152.00</i>	<i>10.40</i>	<i>3.20</i>	<i>0.41</i>
<i>2005-06</i>	<i>771.10</i>	<i>288.20</i>	<i>154.00</i>	<i>11.50</i>	<i>5.00</i>	<i>0.35</i>
<i>2010-11</i>	<i>793.60</i>	<i>302.40</i>	<i>163.00</i>	<i>12.20</i>	<i>6.50</i>	<i>0.46</i>

Source: Minisrty of Human resource development

India has the largest number of academic institutions in the world in terms of higher education and is the third in the world in terms of enrolment, after China and the US. However, only 7 per cent in the age group of 18-24 enroll for higher education in India and this is only one-

half of Asia's average. On a brighter note, however, enrolments have been increasing steadily in higher education in the past 2 decades from 3.4 million in 1984-85 to 11.03 million in 2005-06. In addition to a medium of livelihood, higher education is also now regarded as an instrument of infrastructure for social and economic change. Fundamental policy changes at the grassroots level in issues pertaining to curriculum, infrastructure, governance, and funding are taking place to make India's higher education a socially and economically viable option in a competitive world. Factors such as e-learning, distance education, public private partnerships coupled with international collaborations and exchange programmes are changing the face of higher education in India. The higher education system in India has changed its unidirectional approach and is slowly transitioning into producing professionals with better quality education. Traditional programmes are adopting innovative measures to encourage enrolment and institutes are promoting research based practices. Efforts are being made to move from the theoretical base to a more 'real-world' and career-oriented approach. On the flip side, India's education system continues to grapple with deficiencies such as a rigid system, lack of funding, inadequate infrastructure, demand supply gaps, urban-rural divide, and scarcity of skilled manpower.

Critical issues in Indian higher education:

As India strives to compete in a globalised economy in areas that require highly trained professionals, the quality of higher education becomes increasingly important. So far, India's large, educated population base and its reservoir of at least moderately welltrained university graduates have aided the country in moving ahead, but the competition is fierce; from China in particular. Other countries are also upgrading higher education with the aim of building world class universities. Even the small top tier of higher education faces serious problems. Many IIT graduates, well trained in technology, have chosen not to contribute their skills to the burgeoning technology sector in India; perhaps half leave the country immediately upon graduation to pursue advanced studies abroad, and most do not return. A stunning 86 per cent of Indian students in the fields of science and technology who obtain degrees in the United States do not return home immediately following their graduation. A body of dedicated and able teachers work at the IITs

and IIMs, but the lure of jobs abroad and in the private sector makes it increasingly difficult to lure the best and brightest to the academic profession. The present system of higher education does not serve the purpose for which it has been started. In general education itself has become so profitable a business that quality is lost in the increase of quantity of professional institutions with quota system and politicization adding fuel to the fire of spoil system, thereby increasing unemployment of graduates without quick relief to mitigate their sufferings in the job market of the country. So, the drawbacks of the higher education system underscore the need for reforms to make it worthwhile and beneficial to all concerned. Most observers agree that Indian higher education, the significant and impressive developments of the past few decades notwithstanding, faces major challenges in both quantitative and qualitative terms. Perhaps the clearest and boldest statement of this issue can be found in the “Report to the Nation 2006” of the National Knowledge Commission which concludes that there is ‘a quiet crisis in higher education in India that runs deep’, and that it has to do with both the quantity and the quality of higher education in India. Recognizing this dual challenge, the Indian Prime Minister, Manmohan Singh, severely criticized in a recent speech the serious qualitative deficiencies in Indian higher education while at the same time announcing plans for a major expansion of the system. Reflecting on the findings of a confidential report by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council, which is affiliated to the University Grants Commission (UGC), he expressed his concern over the fact that two thirds (68%) of the country’s universities and 90 percent of its colleges are “of middling or poor quality” and that well over half of the faculty in India’s colleges do not have the appropriate degree qualifications. Knowledge is the base for overall growth and if the nation has to be competitive and to be at par with the globalization pace, we will have to respond to the market forces. According to a study only 25% of engineering graduates are directly employable (Infosys, an IT giant, last year sorted through 1.3 million applicants only to find that around two percent were qualified for jobs.) Quality of education delivered in most institutions is very poor. While India has some institutions of global repute delivering quality education, such as (Indian Institute of Management) IIMs and (Indian Institute of Technology) IITs, we do not have enough of them. It has very narrow range of course options that are offered and education is a seller’s market, where is no scope of incentive to provide quality education. There is clearly a lack of

educated educators and teaching is not an attractive profession. It's a last choice in terms of career. Number of Ph.D.s produced each year is very low and those required by academia is far higher. In fact, at many institutions fresh graduates are employed to teach, leading to poor quality of classroom instruction. Most of the education institutions esp. in states such as Maharashtra and states in South India are owned by politicians. This Education system which is highly regulated by the government has been set up to benefit politicians. The growth of higher education in India has been largely guided by the serviceable prerequisite of the economy. After independence, the role of the state in planning out a development path and also in building higher education institutions was guided by mutuality of purpose. Most observers of higher education in India feel that performance of higher education institutions has been less than satisfactory in terms of access, equity and quality. Now there is an urgent need to work for the development of the educational sector to meet the need of the emerging opportunities, increasing younger generation population and challenges of the 21st century.

Challenges of present higher educational system in India:

Since we have got independence we are facing challenges to establish a great and strong education system. Various governments came and gone. Off course they tried to establish new education policies in the system but this is very sad to dictate that they were not sufficient for our country. Still we are facing lot of problems and challenges in our Education System. India recognises that the new global scenario poses unprecedented challenges for the higher education system. The University Grants Commission has appropriately stated that a whole range of skills will be demanded from the graduates of humanities, social sciences, natural sciences and commerce, as well as from the various professional disciplines such as agriculture, law, management, medicine or engineering. India can no longer continue the model of general education as it has been persisting in for the large bulk of the student population. Rather, it requires a major investment to make human resource productive by coupling the older general disciplines of humanities, social sciences, natural sciences and commerce to their applications in the new economy and having adequate field based experience to enhance knowledge with skills and develop appropriate attitudes.

Responding to these emerging needs, the UGC stated: "The University has a crucial role to play in promoting social change. It must make an impact on the community if it is to retain its legitimacy and gain public support". It seeks to do so by a new emphasis on community based programmes and work on social issues. Concepts of access, equity, relevance and quality can be operationalised only if the system is both effective and efficient. Hence, the management of higher education and the total networking of the system has become an important issue for effective management. The shift can occur only through a systemic approach to change as also the development of its human resource, and networking the system through information and communication technology. There are many basic problems facing higher education in India today. These include inadequate infrastructure and facilities, large vacancies in faculty positions and poor faculty thereof, low student enrolment rate, outmoded teaching methods, declining research standards, unmotivated students, overcrowded classrooms and widespread geographic, income, gender, and ethnic imbalances. Apart from concerns relating to deteriorating standards, there is reported exploitation of students by many private providers. Ensuring equitable access to quality higher education for students coming from poor families is a major challenge. Students from poor background are put to further disadvantage since they are not academically prepared to crack highly competitive entrance examinations that have bias towards urban elite and rich students having access to private tuitions and coaching. Education in basic sciences and subjects that are not market friendly has suffered. Research in higher education institutions is at its lowest ebb. There is an inadequate and diminishing financial support for higher education from the government and from society. Many colleges established in rural areas are non-viable, are under-enrolled and have extremely poor infrastructure and facilities with just a few teachers. A series of judicial interventions over the last two decades and knee-jerk reaction of the government – both at the centre and state level and the regulatory bodies without proper understanding of the emerging market structure of higher education in India has further added confusion to the higher education landscape in the country. There is an absence of a well-informed reform agenda for higher education in the country. A few efforts made now and then are not rooted in the new global realities based on competition and increased mobility of students and workforce. Time to time system influenced with new challenges and government taken a major role to build the

system. But there are many challenges always faced by the government. Some of the leading challenges before the higher education system are continuous upgradation of curriculum to keep in pace with rapid growth of science and technology; globalisation and the resultant challenges from the international universities; grooming of many private institutions without any method of ensuring maintenance of quality and standard; need for adequate funding to meet the demands of various novel innovative programmes; developing a meaningful and purposeful inter-face between the universities, National Research Laboratories, industries, government and society, etc. ICT in higher education policy may not be able to completely overcome all these challenges though it may play a role in information and resource sharing. There are so many people in various parts of country which are still out of reach. This is when we have emphasize more on our education programs and made our system reachable to all areas. Government has to rethink on these areas to implement more on the policies. Money also plays a vital role for the education system which needs to unique for all globally recognized syllabus and curricula. Take a look on our constitution which says that this is the responsibility of central and state government to build good education system. For that we need to have funds. But despite there was a large expenditure on the funds every year on Education where the fund goes and our system remains intact. Central government prepares policies and plan while responsibility of State government is run those policies on ground. The standard education facilities are higher in the states which are much rich. There is a need to change such defects from the country education system which only can be influenced by increasing funding and providing better facilities to students. But we know there is always increase in the fund for the education system but never implemented in that area. So we have to work in this area. Government tries to make different policies which are implemented but quality never checked. Majority of fund goes in the pockets of officials working for this. There is a vast need to improve the quality and standards. The time now is to modernize our education system so that our country can get much more technically graduated people which can help our country to developed state. Today's youth always try to go foreign for his higher education as they have much better facilities and quality of their system. Can't we get that quality here itself? We have to stop this brain drainage so as avoid students to run away from country. Our governments trying for various challenges faced but no one is doing well for that. Government

came and goes but system remains intact. Higher education is extremely diverse and the challenges and issues faced by higher education institutions are just as diverse. The process of education is not merely digesting books. It is also about doing several co-curricular and extra-curricular activities that give a broader meaning to life in general and education in particular. I believe that opportunities for such holistic development are not enough in India. Facilities for the same are lacking or not easily accessible in India. Even where facilities exist, there is a lack of information about the same.

There is a lack of universities and institutes for education but one most important fact is that the quality of education is absent in higher education. There are very few teachers and their knowledge is very insufficient. Most of the teachers are making money with tuitions. I have seen my places where there tuitions. The teachers are not having proper knowledge of subject even and resources to student community are very poor. Students do not have any student-ship ethics, they just want marks in the subject and they study only for grabbing jobs. There is no creativity in students. Our top class students are hard-worker but not innovative. They are not capable enough to produce new technology. There is a great need to revolution in higher education. These are just some challenges which should cover all the aspect in the present scenario of education and we have to implement hard on them.

Suggestions for the development of Higher Education in India:

- Converting 500 existing colleges into universities.
- The Government must provide funds to the private institutions for research and development.
- Relaxing the norms for restrictions on the cap on tuition fees to be collected by the recognized and reputed private institutions.
- The government needs to act with strictness and discretion in development of higher education by penalizing universities that do not meet the stipulated standards & are involved in dilution of standards, unethical practices and excessive commercialization of education.

- A thorough audit of all Government Institutions by international agencies should be executed immediately. Government Institutions are not subject to independent agency scrutiny & evaluations as of now.
- Flexible grading credit based education with the option to transfer between institutions and/or opt for more than a course at a time and multiple specializations across the branches depending on the intellectual capacity.
- Special incentives such as tax rabet to individuals, organizations corporate that contribute to the growth of the educational institution.
- Shifting teaching methodology in institutions from Teaching-Centric to Learning-Centric.

Conclusion:

The paper shows that there is a general argument in favor of increasing investment and expanding access to good quality higher education in India. There is lesser agreement on how funding for expansion will be organized and shared between public and private sectors, between domestic and external agencies, and between households and government. The market orientation in higher education helps to mobilize resources for the expansion of higher education. The government of India needs to redefine its role to suit the changed circumstances. The ideal situation would have been full state funding. The state needs to assume other roles that are equally important, even when it is not in a position to finance all higher education activities. It needs to be more active in developing the rules for establishing institutions, the mechanisms to ensure quality, and the regulations to ensure equity. The state should assume more of a regulatory and facilitative role rather than simply a funding one. The paper has attempted to analyze the influence of global crisis on the demand for higher education and the trends in the globalization of higher education as reflected through the cross-border mobility of institutions, students and teachers. Leaving the education sector to markets may imply that the long-term development contributions of education to nation building might be lost. Since education is one of the important determinants of earning differentials, it can become a source of intergenerational economic and social inequality, unless well planned. Furthermore, leaving the sector to

international markets could lead to a decline in national influence on deciding and designing content and curriculum that could have a long-standing adverse effect on national concerns and development. There is a risk of stratification of students based on their fee-paying capacity. Given the high fee structures, only those from a better economic background will be able to enroll in cross-border and private institutions. This may lead to two types of imbalances in the growth of higher education. First, there are increasing inequalities of access to education and later to employment. Second, there are regional imbalances. Many of the private and cross border education institutions are located in urban areas. Contrary to the general belief that these institutions are absorbing excess demand, they may in fact be increasing the access options of those who already have access to higher education. The impact of the economic crisis on the development of higher education needs to be analyzed more closely. The possibilities for private sector investment in higher education may stagnate or decline. The household response to the crisis is very important. An analysis of the impact of the Concluding observations 29 East Asian economic crisis on higher education clearly showed two patterns: (a) households tend to consume less of everything during a crisis period and this may imply a decline in the demand for higher education; and (b) households re-adjust their budget to keep education investments intact. This happened in many of the crisis-affected countries of East Asia. Universities may be affected by the crisis. Finally, the paper argues for state intervention in higher education rather than leaving the sector mainly to the markets. State intervention with funding support is the ideal situation. In the absence of the possibility of full public funding for higher education development, the state may better target its limited resources to disadvantaged groups and to specific subject areas to improve overall equity in higher education. However, the lack of resources at the disposal of the government should not be a reason for it to be absent from the sector. Even when the state cannot provide funding support, it still has an important role in planning and regulating the system.

References:

1. NavinSingh, Rosemary Papa, "Impact of Globalization in Higher Education", volume-5, number 2(April-June, 2012)
2. Vangelis Tsigiris, "the impact of economic crisis on Higher Education", 18th March 2012, Issue No 213.
3. UNESCO Bangkok, "Asia and Pacific regional Beareau for Education", ISBN 978-9223-400-3.
4. Molly Carbett Board, President, American Council on education, "Higher Education in 2012: a global perspective"
5. MHRD (2006) Annual Report. Ministry of Human Resource Development, Department of Secondary and Higher education. Government of India. New Delhi.
6. Planning Commission (1999) Approach paper to the Tenth Five-year Plan (2002-2007). Planning Commission. New Delhi.
7. Stella, Antony (2002) External quality assurance in Indian higher education: Case study of the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC). International Institute for Educational Planning. Paris. MHRD (2006) Annual Report. Ministry of Human Resource Development, Department of Secondary and Higher education. Government of India. New Delhi.
8. Planning Commission (1999) Approach paper to the Tenth Five-year Plan (2002-2007). Planning Commission. New Delhi.
9. Stella, Antony (2002) External quality assurance in Indian higher education: Case study of the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC). International Institute for Educational Planning. Paris.

10. www.dnb.co.in/universitiesofindia

11. www.cisco.com/web/IN/about/leadership

12. www.aicte-india.org/

13. www.education.nic.in

